

1 **Trim control by commensal restricts immune activation in the gastrointestinal tract.**

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7 We observed disparate control of an E3 ubiquitin ligase controlled by NLR family immune receptor NOD2
8 by commensal and pathogenic gut bacteria demonstrating a specific mechanism for toleragenic properties
9 of commensal bacteria.

10 Citations

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